

REFLECTIONS ON THE IMPACT OF ICT ON TEACHER EDUCATION

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INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is presently a huge, rapidly changing, and rapidly growing field. Similar is its understanding attributed in different contexts and times to the term ICT. Basically, ICT describes a full range of computer hardware, computer software and telecommunication facilities effective in the process of gathering, storing, retrieving, processing, analysing and transmitting information. The term itself evolved from the basic Information Technology (IT), that refers to the key components of computing technology, the software, the hardware and the basic skills required to use a stand-alone computer effectively, for instance for producing handouts or worksheets, to the newer "Information and Communication Technology", a term that adds an extra dimension, that of communication as a means of development. In this sense, ICT covers the use of technology for communication, a key aspect for accomplishing the type of learning we consider meaningful.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) became the backbone of a new era: the information age. This technology influenced practically all walks of Western life. Developing countries should not stay behind in the adoption of ICT. However, if it is to be implemented as a vehicle in development cooperation, the most legitimate question is how ICT actually will be perceived at the grass root level in Less developed countries.

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Due to socio-cultural aspects like traditions, values, political system, economical development and institutional relationships, the meaning of a technology can differ from one region to another and even amongst groups of people. Therefore the local context should be studied in order to make ICT work for local people in less developed regions.

NEED OF ICT IN EDUCATION AND INDUSTRY

After we have understood the basic concept and meaning of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), we move further one step into its application in education. Before that, we must understand the importance of ICT in both education and industry.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become, within a very short time, one of the basic building blocks of modern society. Many countries now regard understanding ICT and mastering the basic skills and concepts of ICT as part of the core of education, alongside reading, writing and numeracy.

In any educational system, the level of available resources places a restriction on the degree to which any new subject can be introduced into the school curriculum, especially where only the most basic facilities have so far been provided. But ICT is of such importance to the future industrial and commercial health of a country that investment in the equipment, teacher education, and support services necessary for the effective delivery of an ICT-based curriculum should rank high in any set of government priorities.

ICT permeates the business environment, it underpins the success of modern corporations, and it provides governments with an efficient infrastructure. At the same time, ICT adds value to the processes of learning, and in the organisation and management of learning institutions. The internet is a driving force for much development and innovation in both developed and developing countries. Countries must be able to benefit from technological developments. To be able to do so, a cadre of professionals has to be educated with ICT background, independent of specific computer platforms or software environment.

The diffusion of ICTs has contributed enormously to the growth of economies in developed nations and developing nations are earnestly facilitating policy frameworks to ensure an equitable diffusion of these technologies.

ICTs refer to the various technologies that enhance the creation, storage, processing, communication and dissemination of information. ICTs also refer to the different infrastructures used in these processes, their applications and the numerous services these infrastructures render. We identify the following technologies as the elements of ICTs:

- Media of Communication (e.g., radio, television)
- Information Machine (e.g., Computers)
- Telecommunications Technologies and Equipment (Satellites, fibre optic cables, phones etc.).

The development in telecommunications has impacted enormously on the applications of ICTs and their uses. Telecommunications technologies, coupled with computer technology have enhanced network-based information and communication platforms, such as the Internet. Telecommunications infrastructures in particular have become the driving forces of ICTs; they have the capability to link all various ICT elements together irrespective of locations and to provide a converging platform for these elements.

The convergence of the various elements of ICTs has enhanced development in all spheres of human activities. *Robin Mansell and Uta Wehn* (1998: 1) state, "advanced microelectronics-based Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are at the heart of recent social and economic transformations in both the industrialised and many developing nations". In 1995 and 1997, the United Nations Commission on Science and Technology for Development (UNCSTD) investigated the benefits and risks of ICTs. The result of this investigation showed many instances where the use of ICTs affords widespread social and economic benefits. There were also many instances where ICTs were making no differences in the lives of people in the developing countries. The result also showed that the diffusion of these technologies is extremely uneven throughout the developing world. As a result of this, there is a high risk that technologies and services will deepen the disadvantages of those without the skills and capabilities to make the investments required for building innovative ICT-based societies (*Mansell & Wehn, 1998:1*).

ICT AND TEACHER EDUCATION

ICTs are one of the major contemporary factors shaping the global economy and producing rapid changes in society. They have fundamentally changed the way people learn, communicate, and do business. They can transform the nature of education – where and how learning takes place and the roles of students and teachers in the learning process.

Education in the different region faces a number of problems. These problems include the shortage of qualified teachers, very large student populations, high drop-out rates of students and teachers, and weak curricula. All of these negative aspects result in poor delivery of education. The education crisis is worsened by the devastating effects of the HIV/AIDS pandemic, increasing poverty, a brain drain in the teaching community, budgetary constraints, poor communication, and inadequate infrastructure. While societies in the region undergo rapid changes as a result of increased access to information, the majority of the school-going youth continue to undergo traditional rote learning. Very little is done to take advantage of the wealth of information available on the Internet. Whereas the processing of information to build knowledge is one of the essential literacy skills vital for the workforce in the 21st century, it is often overlooked in current educational practices.

In order to function in the new world economy, students and their teachers have to learn to navigate large amounts of information, to analyse and make decisions, and to master new knowledge and to accomplish complex tasks collaboratively. Overloaded with information, one key outcome

of any learning experience should be for learners to critically challenge the material collected in order to decide whether it can be considered useful input in any educational activity. This is the basis for the construction of knowledge. The use of ICTs as part of the learning process can be subdivided into three different forms: as object, aspect, or medium (Plomp, ten Brummelhuis, & Pelgrum, 1997).

- As object, one refers to learning about ICTs as specific courses such as 'computer education.' Learners familiarise themselves with hardware and software including packages such as Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, and others. The aim is computer literacy.
- As aspect, one refers to applications of ICTs in education similar to what obtains in industry. The use of ICTs in education, such as in computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing, are examples.
- ICTs are considered as a medium whenever they are used to support teaching and learning.

Technology is not new to education. However, contemporary computer technologies, such as the Internet, allow new types of teaching and learning experiences to flourish. Many new technologies are interactive, making it easier to create environments in which students can learn by doing, receive feedback, and continually refine their understanding and build new knowledge. Access to the Internet gives unprecedented opportunities in terms of the availability of research material and information in general. This availability of research material and information happens to both inspire and threaten teachers.

The computer equipment in the few fortunate schools that have them tends to be underused and lacks appropriate education content. Commonly, the computer equipment is used as objects in computer lessons. A few other subject teachers undertake courses in software packages but are unable to integrate or meaningfully insert this knowledge in their daily teaching work. A worrying tendency is that boys are the targets rather than girls when investments in ICT hardware and training are made (Kinyanjui, 2002). If not taken seriously, this will increase gender disparities in education in the sub-region. Respective governments recognise that ICTs have a critical role to play in improving education and are engaged in drafting ICT policies or ICT chapters in a number of development plans across economic sectors. The policies tend to clearly link development to a forward looking educational sector and increased investment in human resources and ICTs. In the education sector, curriculum review efforts are geared towards modernisation, including the incorporation of important ICT components. However, even the reviewed curricula tend to treat ICT as a subject rather than as an application tool that can be used in all other subjects, in teaching and learning. Very recent discourse indicates that future curriculum reviews may consider a fully fledged ICT mainstreaming process.

Teacher education institutions and programmes have the critical role to provide the necessary leadership in adapting preservice and in-service teacher education to deal with the current demands of society and economy. They need to model the new pedagogies and tools for learning with the aim of enhancing the teaching-learning process. Moreover, teacher education institutions and

programmes must also give guidance in determining how the new technologies can best be used in the context of the culture, needs, and economic conditions of their country.

USE OF ICT IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

The use of the new ICTs in school adds a unique dimension to teaching and learning. As we already emphasised, ICT use invites and caters for a “paradigm shift” regarding teaching and learning, visible in each component of these processes. Here are some specific visible gains:

The type of learning supported in an ICT learning environment tends to be transformative. Thus, different new information and communication means invite for personal interpretation and meaning, evaluation and decision, reasoning and justification, synthesis and conceptualisation, originality, creativity and innovation.

The learning tasks are: open, authentic, problem-based, interpretative, analytical, expressive, inventive. Effective learning with and through ICT would result in: pupils asking more questions and offering hypothesis, as they can answer or explore them; pupils showing a willingness to take risks, because ICT allows them to correct errors or start again; pupils becoming more autonomous, because ICT offers them tools they can control to perform tasks; pupils showing better motivation and willingness to look for answers, because ICT makes information retrieval, data analyses and modelling easier. Effective teaching through ICT would prove that: individual lesson planning takes account of school’s agreed plan for the development of ICT; lesson objectives describe specific opportunities for developing ICT capabilities; teachers take pupils’ prior experience with ICT in account when planning lessons; activities have built-in differentiation so that the tasks match the needs and abilities of pupils; teachers use ICT to motivate and sustain pupils interest; teachers manage their classrooms to maximise the availability and use of ICT tools; teachers use the ICT expertise of colleagues to develop his own knowledge.

ICT FOR QUALITY EDUCATION

The investments of the government and private sectors in Information and Communications Technology (ICT) have indeed contributed access to quality education. Although not all schools in the Philippines are wired to the Internet yet, those with access to ICT tools make the most of the technology. In our region, many of our students and teachers utilise ICT in their learning and teaching. Using ICT tools is fundamental in mining class topics, and in doing school assignments, research work and other scholastic activities.

Students show more enthusiasm in an ICT integrated classroom. We have observed that classroom instructions using traditional tools like chalk and blackboard are becoming less and less appealing to students. We discovered that using computers, LCD projectors and interactive topic exercises not only motivate students but also helps a teacher in managing the classroom. ICT tools save time and enrich students’ learning experience. Because of their interest in the subject and the tools used for instruction, students are inspired to participate in the activities and to learn how

to create and manipulate their own learning tools. Even the teachers challenge themselves to learn more about new teaching strategies. Teachers should use audio-visual presentations and even introduce recorded lessons in their classes.

With the onset of ICT integration in education, today's teachers, regardless of what subject they teach, need to acquire new skills that will enable them to maximise the potentials of ICT and the Internet. Basic skills include the use of e-mail, designing lesson presentations, making grades on spreadsheets, creating simple letters and programmes, research work and even online content development. The acquisition of these skills is needed, or else, the full potential and relevance of the Internet in educational studies won't be realised by the students. With regards to online shared learning, teachers today should also recognise that learning should not be limited in the classroom. With the Internet, collaborative projects can be undertaken where two or more classes or groups from various geographical locations can work on a common project.

The success of ICT integration in education can be achieved through the collaboration of teachers, school administrators, government and private sectors. Investing in education wins big. Investing in ICT for quality education reaps greater rewards for the youth, the teachers, and our future.

CONCLUSION

Changing Technology is a part of the rapidly changing social, cultural, political and economic times in which we live. Both administrators and teachers in schools, however, are ill equipped to deal with the enormity and complexity of the technological change and going on around us. In relative terms, our programme of study and schools at sites of learning are largely low tech learning contexts in a high-tech world. If this does not change, there will rapidly become redundant. The pressure to examine the new technologies and to see how they square against the existing curricula is placing stress on the educational bureaucracy. Therefore; there is a need to change in each and every sphere of society according to the time of Information and Communication Technology. It has the ability to enhance every type of development in the society. Education is the only means to incorporate Information and Communication Technology in the development aspects of the society.

Information and Communication Technology can also be used as a tool to improve the quality of education for preparing the society and its manpower to face the challenge of future. A characteristic of ICT is its phenomenal rate of growth, in magnitude as well as complexity. Rates of obsolescence are also high. As Information and Communication Technologies get more sophisticated, so do educational technologies that are essentially the applications of Information and Communication Technologies in the classrooms. Consequently, the speed by which the Government and specifically education bureau curacies can formulate policies, plan forward or even simply react are put to the rest. The change in education should be according to the need of the change. It needs a changed and pragmatist mind set among the teachers and policy-makers.

References

Khvilon, E., Patru, M., (2002). *Information and Communication Technologies in Teacher Education. A planning guide*, UNESCO Division of Higher Education, Paris

Butter, G.W. & Zwinfer: *Learning with IT: The issue* (2001).

Gill (N.S.), Dabas (K.C.); Dabas (S), impact of information technologies on social development, XLII All India Library Conference Volume, Calicut, Dec 21-24, 1996.

Nwosu, P., C. Onwumechili and R.M. Bayo (eds.) (1995). *Communication and the transformation of society; a developing regions perspective*, pp 181-192. Lanham, MD: University Press of America.

Pandey, G.P. and Joya Chakroborty: *University News* 40 (8) 11 (2002).

Singhal, Arvind and E.M. Rogers (1998). *Indias Information Revolution*, New Delhi: Sage Publications.

ICT and the World View-

ICT is a force that has changed many aspects of the way we live. It has led to a new way of thinking and a new way of doing things. It has brought us closer together and has made the world a smaller place.

NEW ROLE OF TEACHER IN THE POST-MODERN PERIOD

The role of the teacher in the post-modern period is changing. Teachers are no longer just transmitters of knowledge. They are now facilitators, guides, and learners themselves. They are helping students to develop critical thinking skills and to become active participants in their own learning.

ICT has brought us a new era of civilization in which education has become a continuous process. It has changed the way we learn and the way we teach. Teachers are now using technology to enhance their instruction and to provide personalized learning experiences for their students.

The use of hardware and software for efficient management of information, storage retrieval, processing, communication, dissemination and sharing of information for social, economic and cultural development (UNESCO, 2000). The explosive nature of knowledge and its application in the world of work has brought a compulsive need for learning and teaching. Learning has provided an extended arena for the user in both the world of ICT and the world of work. It has provided a new arena for the user in both the world of ICT and the world of work.

B-learning is the latest buzz word in the education circle today which comes under the umbrella of ICT. This greatly enhances the way the education is imparted to the individual. This concept is not a new one as it has been around since the advent of the IBM. The standard and the investment in ICT has been increasing steadily. It has become a part of our lives and we are using it every day.